

ADTRH1, a short-duration promising rice hybrid

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Heterosis breeding in rice is a new and practical approach that aims to break the yield plateau. TRRI Aduthurai started research on heterosis in 1986 and released its first rice hybrid, ADTRH1, in January 1998 for general cultivation.

ADTRH1 is the heterotic combination of a three-line breeding system involving cytoplasmic genic male sterile, maintainer, and restorer lines—A, B, and R. IR58025A and IR66R are the parents of rice hybrid ADTRH1. This hybrid is semidwarf (105 cm) and matures in 115 d. It tillers profusely (12–15 productive tillers hill⁻¹) under 20 × 10-cm spacing, with each panicle 27.5 cm long, producing 142 grains, and with more than 90% spikelet fertility. Its 1,000-grain weight is 23.8 g.

In different trials, ADTRH1 showed 26.9% and 24.5% higher yield over CORH1 and ASD18, respectively, with an average yield of 6.6 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). The hybrid recorded the highest grain yield of 11.4 t ha⁻¹ in 1 out of 77 adaptive research trials in farmers' fields in Tamil Nadu. The highest yield of the check in these trials was 9.6 t ha⁻¹.

ADTRH1 possesses long slender white kernels with a mild aroma when cooked. Physical, cooking, chemical, and organoleptic traits are all good (Table 2). Its grains contain 25.2% amylose and 6.9% protein. It is moderately resistant to stem borer and leaffolder under field conditions and moderately susceptible to blast and green leafhopper under glasshouse screening (Table 3). It is recommended for cultivation in irrigated transplanted areas during both the wet (April–September) and dry seasons in Tamil Nadu.

Table 1. Performance of ADTRH1 compared with CORH1 and ASD18.

Variety/hybrid	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) in				Mean (t ha ⁻¹)
	Station trials, ^a 1994-97	Multilocation trials, ^b 1996-98	Adaptive research ^c trials, 1997	Large-scale demonstration, ^d 1997	
ADTRH1	6.6 a	6.2 a	6.5 a	7.1 a	6.6
CORH1	5.1 c	4.9 c	5.7 b	4.9 b	5.2
ASD18	5.3 b	5.4 b	5.7 b	4.8 b	5.3

^aMean of 4 trials. ^bMean of 19 trials. ^cMean of 77 trials. ^dMean of 6 trials. Means followed by similar letters do not differ significantly from each other by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Quality characteristics of hybrid ADTRH1.

Character	ADTRH1	IR58025A	IR58025B	IR66R	CORH1	ASD18
<i>Physical characteristics (% in rough rice)</i>						
Hulling	79.8	78.8	76.0	82.0	78.0	75.2
Milling	77.1	74.1	68.4	78.2	65.5	69.3
Head rice recovery	69.9	66.0	58.2	71.6	63.5	59.1
<i>Cooking quality characteristics</i>						
Weight increase (g)	26.5	26.0	26.2	26.0	24.7	25.5
Volume increase (mL)	30.2	28.0	29.0	30.0	24.8	28.0
Water absorption (mL)	28.5	28.5	28.0	28.0	24.0	28.0
Cooking time (min)	24.0	25.0	24.0	24.0	22.0	25.0
PS5 BX	2.3	2.5	2.8	2.5	—	2.9
<i>Organoleptic evaluation (1–9 scale)</i>						
Color and appearance	3.9	3.8	3.7	4.0	3.0	3.7
Flavor	3.9	3.8	3.7	4.0	3.5	3.8
Texture	3.9	3.8	3.7	3.9	3.7	3.7
Paste	4.0	4.0	3.9	4.0	3.5	3.8
Overall acceptability	4.0	4.0	3.9	4.0	3.7	3.8

Note: Scale of 1–9, with 1 = good and 9 = bad.

Table 3. Reaction of ADTRH1 and other varieties/hybrids against pests and diseases.

Pest	Center ^a	Year	Score (1–9 scale)			
			ADTRH1	CORH1	ASD18	TNI
<i>Insects</i>						
Stem borer	Aduthurai (F)	1995-96	3	3	3	7
	Aduthurai (F)	1996-97	3	1	3	7
Leaffolder	Aduthurai (F)	1997-98	3	1	3	3
	Coimbatore (A)	1995-96	5	5	9	9
Green leafhopper						
<i>Disease</i>						
Blast	Aduthurai (A)	1995-96	5	7	5	—
	Aduthurai isolate					
	Coimbatore (A)	1996-97	5	NT ^b	0	—
	Coimbatore isolate					

^aF = field condition, A = artificial condition. ^bNT = not tested. Note: Scale of 1–9, with 1 = resistant and 9 = susceptible.